

The first network-arch railway bridge using cold bent HD profiles E30 railway line bridge over Vistula river in Cracow (Poland) constructed in 2023

Bogusław Pilujski^a, Dariusz Sobala^a, Radosław Sęk^b,
Wojciech Lorenc^{*:c}, Maciej Kozuch^c, Wojciech Ochojski^d

^aStrabag

boguslaw.pilujski@strabag.com, dariusz.sobala@strabag.com,

^bRS Projekt, Poland

radoslawsek@rs-projekt.pl

^cWrocław University of Science and Technology, Dept. of Civil, Environmental, Poland

wojciech.lorenc@pwr.edu.pl, maciej.kozuch@pwr.edu.pl

^dArcelorMittal, Poland

wojciech.ochojski@arcelormittal.com

ABSTRACT

The new network arch bridges along the E-30 railway line crossing the Vistula River in the center of Krakow in Poland represent a significant step in bridge engineering. The superstructure of each span is a form of network arch which is characterized by a very slender arch and deck. The entire bridge consists of three independent bridges (M-1 double-tracks, M-2 single-track, M-3 single-track with pedestrian walkway), each with three arch spans of different length. The first bridge was put into service in 2020 and the entire bridge has been finalized in 2023. The innovative solutions provided in the construction are as follows: 1) The first railway bridge using the cold-bent I-rolled profiles (HDs). 2) A new type of composite element formed from two curved T-sections connected by a concrete infill in the space between using composite dowels shear connection. This is a completely new type of structural element. 3) For the first time a T-section (that was cut out from the rolled I-beam to obtain composite dowels) was cold-bent in the plane of the flange. 4) The composite dowels used are the thickest used in construction to date. 5) New types of hanger anchorages (in the arch and in the deck). 6) K-type joints were used instead of X-joints (new solutions for such thick walls). 7) Development of a new hanger-deck anchorage using prestressed composite dowels.

Keywords: cold-bending, HD sections, network-arch bridge, composite dowels

1 INTRODUCTION

The new network arch bridges along the E-30 railway line (Fig. 1) crossing the Vistula River in the center of Kraków (southern Poland) represent a significant step in bridge engineering. The superstructure of each span is a form of network arch which is characterized by a very slender arch and deck (Fig. 2). The entire bridge consists of three independent bridges (M-1 double-tracks, M-2 single-track, M-3 single-track with pedestrian walkway; see Fig. 3), each with three arch spans of different length. The concept of three bridges of this type was proposed by Strabag's CEO Mr. Bogusław Pilujski, and to implement the proposed form, the achievements of recent years, already proven in Polish bridges, were used: cold-bent HD profiles and composite dowels. The superstructure of each span is a new form of network arch, whose basic elements are cold-bent HD rolled sections (normally used in high-rise buildings) and new composite elements using T-sections connected to the concrete body using composite dowels (which are also used in hanger plates for two-track bridges). For example, in the 116m span, a HD400x818 profile with 97mm flange thickness and 60.5mm web

thickness made of S460HISTAR steel has been used. The prestressed concrete deck is suspended to the arch using hangers made of round bars. The bridge has been designed for $\alpha=1.21$ according to PN-EN 1991-2:2007. Formal design issues leading to the creation of the alternative design that was ultimately implemented are presented in (1).

Fig. 1. General view of completed bridge (picture: Piotr Hamarnik, PKP Polskie Linie Kolejowe S.A)

Fig. 2. Longitudinal section of the bridge

Fig. 3. Transversal section of the bridge (from the left: M3, M1, M2).

2 TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC BACKGROUND

The resulting structure is the world's first railway bridge made of cold-bent HD sections (and subsequently, as a consequence, a number of other innovative solutions were adopted). One may ask why Tveit's idea (2), which is not new, has not been applied to a railway bridge yet? The answer is simple: necessity is the mother of inventions and appropriate conditions are also required for their creation, and, according to the authors, such a situation seems to be currently occurring in Poland on the bridge market. At the beginning, it should be noted that in Poland the design-build or alternative design formula generally apply on the market; i.e. the contractor decides on the solution (and the criterion is, of course, the price). In the case of solutions that are important from the point of view of architecture, the aspect of appearance is of course taken into account and agreed upon, and that was the case here. The bridge is a response to economic requirements: this solution was simply economical and this aspect outweighed the resistance to testing something new (for other aspects see (1)). Firstly, the bridge was implemented by a large company (Strabag), but the design involved mainly individual and independent people, supervised by one designer who did not represent any large company but basically operated independently on the market (so he is free to choose his co-workers/consultancy). In this way, flexibility, decisiveness and openness to new solutions are possible. Secondly, proven solutions were used, but they were applied in a new field: the first global use of a cold-bent HD sections (HDs) for bridge construction took place (also in Poland) over 10 years ago in the case of a road bridge, and since then many road structures up to a span of 120 m have been built and valuable experience has been gained (3). In parallel, new solutions for the use of composite dowels (CDs) have been invented for over 10 years (4); and in the case of this bridge, both paths (HDs and CDs) simply "intersected". The remaining new solutions are a consequence of these two basic decision variables, bearing in mind that the arches had to be connected to the concrete deck using hangers.

3 SCOPE OF THE REPORT AND NEW INFORMATION

The structure actually consists of 3 independent bridges (M1, M2, M3) and each of them has three independent spans. The division into three bridges resulted primarily from the need to maintain railway traffic. Construction took 4 years and the M2 single-track bridge was the first to be put into operation. At the same time, further experience was gained and the process of designing subsequent bridges coincided with the construction of the previous ones. Therefore, slightly different (newer) solutions were used in the M1 and M3 bridges. Moreover, the evolution also concerned calculation methods, especially in the context of hangers' pretensioning.

The purpose of this publication is, in addition to presenting the completed bridge as a whole and reflections on the investment, to show experiences from the M1 and M3 double-track bridges that have not been published, while referring the reader to already available publications from the period of construction of the M2 bridge. In this way, a relatively complete assessment of the issue is possible. And so, first information about the bridge design and the first experiences after the completion of the bridge spans for the first track (M2) are presented (in English) in (1). This first bridge (it was IABSE Shortlisted Project; <https://iabse.org/Awards/Shortlisted>) was put into service in 2020 and the entire bridge has been finalized in 2023, after completion of spans of M3 bridge. The idea for a new hybrid element consisting of two T-sections connected with concrete using CDs (Fig. 4) and its application in the M2 bridge is shown in (5). Issues related to construction technology (all bridges) are presented in (6). Due to the subject of the conference, this publication focuses on issues related to the steel structure (the bridge deck is made of prestressed concrete).

Fig. 4. General view of new hybrid elements in the bridge M1 (picture by P. Hamarnik)

4 STEEL ARCHES

The main elements of the curved steel girders (Fig. 5) were designed from cold-formed I-sections, to which gusset plates have been welded. Typical HD (normally used in high-rise buildings) and HL profiles (for arch-deck connections) were used. The arches are connected to each other by tubular pipes in ‘K’ system. The I-girders were made of S460HISTAR steel (which has a very low yield strength reduction depending on thickness) while the other of the elements were made of typical S355 steel grade. The thickness of the flanges used varies up to 140mm.

The profiles have been delivered to Poland already cold-bent by their manufacturer, ArcelorMittal in Luxembourg (without any additional steel elements like anchor plates). In parallel to production, the laboratory of Wrocław Univ. of Science and Technology tested the bending process using optical fibres (Fig. 6), simulated it using FEM and provided a scientific analysis of the bending process.

Fig. 5. Production of steel arches by ArcelorMittal

Fig. 6. Tests of cold bending procedure in Wrocław University of Science and Technology: measuring using light wires

Additional steel plates have been welded in Poland (Fig. 7) and their construction, however it looks simple, required quite much effort for investigation, relatively big fatigue forces governed the design and the structure of the anchoring plate is quite different than one used for road bridges (Fig. 8). It is worth remembering that because we are dealing with crossed tendons (network arch), the connection

is eccentric, which results in high stress concentrations in the welds connecting the plate with the profile (and twisting of the arch, but this is a separate issue).

Fig. 7. Elements of steel arch during production in Poland

Fig. 8. Details of hanger's connection with steel arch

On-site K-type welds (Fig. 9) were used to connect segments of arch (they were like about 10m long), so quite large number of costly welding was used. This was the reason to implement optimisation and K welds instead of X welds are used. Welding of S460 very thick steel elements required special consideration and effort too. The geometry of such a thick weld must be associated with appropriate holes at the weld approach due to weld shrinkage (7). Paper (7) presents considerations regarding welding of HD sections (FE vs tests and analytical consideration); one can consider that the welding type that is used in Poland differs from the one presented in (7).

Fig. 9. K-welds of steel elements

As already mentioned, optimizations were made as the work progressed and experience was gained; on the M3 bridge, which was constructed last, a concept with web-strengthening cover-plates was used (Fig. 10), because the loss of section (with thick webs of the HD profile) turned out to be an important economic factor. An interesting issue turned out to be the tolerance of the production of HD sections in the context of their subsequent connection. In one connection, deviations of web axis slightly exceeding the limit made it necessary to use an individual solution in the form of a cover-plate welded in the plane of the flanges and of a longer length. To sum up, such compact sections (HDs) require some special consideration regarding connections; both between them and with additional elements.

Fig. 10. Connection of steel segments using additional coverplates on the steel web

5 CONSTRUCTION OF THE BRIDGE

Of course, making the arch segments was possible after setting up the hybrid starting segments and constructing a concrete deck. Construction of the bridge was a challenging task and it is described in (6) and in (1) construction of M2 bridge is shortly presented. Herein only some aspects are presented. The arch was made until it was closed in its upper point. The construction technology is shown schematically in Fig. 11 (6). Bridge under construction is shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 11. Technology of construction of main span (6)

Fig. 12. Construction of main span (6)

Although the construction of the bridge was a complicated task, in this paper the issues of technology are not the main subject of the analysis and the focus is further on presenting new structural elements used for the first time: a hybrid arch segment (the hybrid arch root) and a new type of anchoring the hanger in the bridge. The idea of hybrid arch segment is for the first time presented in (5), where the concept of the element is described for purposes of M2 bridge and the structure used in the M2 bridge is shown.

6 THE HYBRID ARCH ROOT IN M1 AND M3 BRIDGES

HL section was used in M2 bridge (5). After the design stage and the subsequent process of construction of the M2 bridge, valuable experience was gained and a number of modifications have been implemented for the next two bridges, as a result. The biggest change was the replacement of HL sections by HD sections in the arch root. This was due to the following reasons: first of all, it was observed that material waste after HL cutting was relatively high, so it was decided to decrease this amount and implement a longitudinal welding connection instead. The modification entailed using a T-profile made of a straight-cut HD shape (such as the adjoining one) and longitudinal butt welding a CD-strip (plate with MCL steel dowels) of a thickness less than the thickness of the T-profile web used in main (the biggest) spans of M1 and M3 bridges (Figs. 13,14,15). This thickness is 60mm and this is also the largest thickness of steel dowels used in industry. Their capacity is relatively high and it would not have been economically justified to increase the dimensions and thickness parallel to T-section increase (in HL sections their size was strictly dependent on the web’s thickness due to shaping from the same T-section). Taking those arguments into account, it appeared to be a very successful approach. The element was designed according to “hybrid concept” that is going to be introduced in new CEN-TS 1994-1-102 specification in the near future (currently it is out of scope of simplified design procedure presented in EN 1994).

Fig. 13. Steel part of arch root for M1 bridge: 1,2 - half of HD section, 3 - strip with steel dowels of thickness 60mm

Fig. 14. The arch roots of M3 bridge using composite dowels: steel parts

Fig. 15. The arch roots of M1 bridge and construction of reinforcement of concrete deck (with completed M2 bridge at the background)

7 A NEW TYPE OF ANCHORING STEEL HANGERS IN THE DECK

Unlike the solution with headed studs used in the anchors in the M2 bridge, a new type of anchorage using composite dowels is used in the M1 and M3 bridges (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16. The solution used in M2 bridge (left) and a new type of anchorage using composite dowels is used in the M1 and M3 bridges (right).

Due to the innovative nature of the solution, fiber optic measurements (Fig. 17) were carried out during tension and the results were verified with the design assumptions.

Fig. 17. The fiber optic measurements of the steel element: light wires and (for reference only) the results of strains

The obtained results confirmed that due to transverse prestressing (used in M1 and M3 bridges, contrary to M2 bridge; see Fig. 18 at the left), most of the force from the hanger is transferred to concrete through friction.

Fig. 18. Transversal prestressing ducts crossing the steel anchorage (left) and fiber optic measurements while tensioning hangers

8 PRETENSIONING OF HANGERS

MACALLOY system hangers with different diameters and allowable stress amplitude $\Delta\sigma_c=105\text{MPa}$ has been used. Tensioning procedure is presented in Fig. 18. The basic issue that attracts attention is the appropriate modeling of the tensioning procedure using FEM and then obtaining convergence of the designed forces on the structure. This requires close cooperation between the contractor and the designer. Of course, the bars should be pretensioned in such a way that there is no compression in characteristic combinations. However, it should be noted that designing and modeling the pretensioning procedure is incomparably more complicated than, for example, in the case of a suspended or extrados bridges. This is a complicated procedure that requires a lot of experience and modeling skills, in particular when there are non-linearities related to sag and rheology (anchoring in a concrete deck). Since engineers in Poland have been designing and building similar road bridges for some time (3), the necessary experience has already been gained and these procedures are mastered. In the described structure, where there are hangers with a significant inclination and a concrete deck, these issues are probably the most complicated compared to other structures.

Fig. 19. The bridge in operation (all 3 bridges)

9 SUMMARY

The innovative construction of the railway bridge (Fig. 19) is presented and the new solutions used are highlighted. First of all, valuable experience in design and construction was gained. The experience gained allows for further development and design of other new structures, and such structures are currently being designed and constructed. In particular, the new anchors presented are currently being designed in an optimized form in a new arch railway bridge with a span of 120 m. For more information just type “e30 railway bridge in Cracow” in Google search; there is a lot of pictures and movies of the bridge during construction and in the final stage.

REFERENCES

1. *Bridge over Vistula river in Cracow: the first railway network arch bridge using cold-bent HD sections and composite dowels.* **Sęk, Radosław, et al.** Wrocław : IABSE Symposium 7-9 October 2020, 2020. pp. 155-161.
2. **Tveit, Per.** An Introduction to the Network Arch. *Lectures at NTNU Trondheim on August 15th 2006.* 2006.
3. **Kaczmarek, Tomasz, et al.** Polish experience with network arch bridges using cold-bent HD sections. *Steel Construction.* 2020, 13.
4. *Composite dowels: the way to the new forms of steel-concrete composite structures.* **Lorenc, Wojciech.** Wrocław : IABSE Symposium 7-9 October 2020, 2020.
5. *New type of composite arch element using composite dowels: application in railway network arch bridge.* **Sęk, Radosław, et al.** Stromberg, Germany, July 26-30, 2021 : 9 TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE CONSTRUCTION IN STEEL AND CONCRETE, 2021. 7th European conference on steel and composite structures. p. 301.
6. *Technologia budowy mostu M1 nad Wisłą w Krakowie i związane z tym wyzwania (The technology and experience of construction bridge M1 over the Vistula River in Cracow).* **Ostrzolek, Wojciech.** Wrocław : WDM (Wrocław Bridge Days), 2021.
7. **Zanon, Riccardo, et al.** Tied-arch bridges with jumbo shapes as arch member. State of the art and developments. *CONSTRUZIONI METALLICHE.* 2020, Mar/Apr.